

Religion at Erlitou

also known as “Religious development in prehistoric China”, “Capital of the Xia dynasty”, “Chinese early state religion”, “Religion in archaeology”, “Religious materiality”

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Entry tags: Prehistoric Religion, Early Chinese Traditions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Technology, Religious Group, Neolithic, Tomb, Chinese Religion, Divination

The site of Erlitou is one of the most important sites for the study of the Bronze Age in central China (1800 BCE – 206 BCE). It was discovered by the well-known archaeologist Xu Xusheng in 1959, who led a team in search of the Xia capitals based on the later historical texts. Decades of excavations have yielded tremendously rich amounts of material remains, offering first-hand data for the analysis of the early development of technology, religion, social evolution, long-distance cultural communication and other key aspects of the Central Plains of China. It is often regarded as the beginning of the Bronze Age in central China, although bronze metallurgy was introduced via the Eurasia Steppe and performed in China in much earlier periods in the north and northwest. More importantly, it was Erlitou people who combined the newly arrived metallurgy with the long extant ceramic vessels and invented bronze ritual vessels, which distinguished China from all other parts of Eurasia and dominated the Chinese Bronze Age for nearly two thousand years. The abstract animal faces on these bronze ritual vessels, together with jades, dragon-shaped sceptres decorated with turquoise and other exotic objects or materials, indicates the presence of supernatural beings in the perception of the Erlitou people. Further indication comes from the large amount of human and animal sacrifices, sometimes neatly arranged in the ceremonial pits. There is also evidence of divination, which used the cracks that resulted from firing the animal bones to predict the future, a tradition that was inherited from the late Neolithic periods and continued to the late Shang Anyang when oracle bones were widely discovered. Recent excavations reveal clear urban planning at Erlitou. The entire site (ca. 3 km²) had been divided into nine sections by two north-south roads and two east-west roads crossed with each other. Along the central north-south line, which becomes the one most important land marker in urban designing in later Chinese dynasties, lay the ritual/ceremonial section, palatial section and craft section. Various types of burials and rammed-earth mounds suggest large gatherings and that ritual or religious activities played a vital role in the social organization at Erlitou. Given the massive scale of organization and many pioneering achievements at Erlitou, there is no doubt that the ritual system played a critical part, within which a number of elements could be related to religion. Unfortunately, no sign of writing has yet been recovered, making it very challenging to distinguish ritual with religion or perform finer-grained research on various aspects of religion at Erlitou.

Date Range: 1800 BCE - 1500 BCE

Region: Erlitou Yanshi, Henan

Region tags: China, Henan Province, Erlitou village, Yanshi city

The site of Erlitou is located south of the Luo River. It covers the modern-day village Erlitou and overlaps with a few other neighbouring villages under the Yanshi city.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: IA CASS (Institute of Archaeology, Chinese Academy of Social Science 中国社会科学院考古研究所). 2014. Erlitou: 1999–2006. Beijing: Wenwu Chubanshe (in Chinese)
- Source 2: Allan, S., 2007. Erlitou and the formation of Chinese civilization: Toward a new paradigm. *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 66(2), pp.461-496.
- Source 3: Zhang, C., Pollard, A., Rawson, J., Huan, L., Liu, R., & Tang, X. (2019). China's major Late Neolithic centres and the rise of Erlitou. *Antiquity*, 93(369), 588-603. doi:10.15184/aqy.2019.63

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.eltxdmuseum.com/main>
- Source 1 Description: The official website of the Erlitou museum (also known as the Museum of the Xia Dynasty) is extremely useful for understanding the material culture of Erlitou and related subjects. It does not only include many well-known artefacts of Erlitou (<https://www.eltxdmuseum.com/zhenpin>), but also 3D exhibition for the whole museum (<https://www.eltxdmuseum.com/chenzhan/c/53>).

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Erlitou_culture
- Source 1 Description: Very few textual corpora online are related to Erlitou. Wikipedia provides a relatively updated picture of the site and the broad archaeological culture it represents.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Field doesn't know

Notes: After decades of excavation, neither Erlitou nor Erligang (Zhengzhou) has yielded any sign of writing. It is either because these records were not easily preserved in deposition (e.g., organic materials) or they never existed.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The religion represented by Erlitou can be only understood through material remains and unfortunately, no written records have been discovered. There appears no doubt that Erlitou people were in frequent contact with other groups from different directions and many religion-related objects such as jade, bronze ritual vessels and dragon-shaped turquoise show a close connection with the late Neolithic people and other contemporary groups.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Only some house foundations (rammed-earth) and associated ceremonial pits or burials have been discovered in the ritual and palatial section at Erlitou. The house foundations show in round or square, ranging from a few to circa one hundred square metres. In ceremonial pits or burials are often discovered elite objects such as jade, bronzes, lacquer, or turquoise.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

–Percentage: 12.5

Notes: The ritual/ceremonial section in the north of Erlitou is often regarded as religious. Plus a few places in the palatial section which were also likely religious, the overall percentage could be around 10-15%

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

–Square meters: 84

Notes: This is the largest house foundation which can be associated with ritual practice at Erlitou (84YLVI, north-south 12 meters and east-west 7 meters).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

–Percentage of area: 12.5

Notes: Erlitou was the largest settlement in this period.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: So far, it is still extremely difficult to provide an estimation of the overall population size at Erlitou, not to mention a specific type of people.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although no solid evidence can be provided, it appears that Erlitou normally invested a considerable amount of social wealth (animals, crops, or human sacrifices) in the ritual ceremonies, which were very likely related to certain type(s) of religion. This certainly required a system for collection and mobilization of these key resources. Therefore assigning religious affiliation could be envisaged.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Some tombs are very likely to be associated with religious activities, particularly those located in the ritual section of Erlitou. The elite tombs are also likely related to religion but difficult to tell precisely in which aspects.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Some house foundations are round, indicative of altars at Erlitou.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Many ceremonial pits are excavated with animal sacrifices and other material wealth (e.g., jade). For instance, some animal remains were carefully laid out, suggesting a deliberate decision.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some large houses around a few hundred square metres could be used for mass gathering point. But it is hard to tell whether it is specifically related to religion.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As noted in the previous question.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Whilst nobody knows this for certainty, it should be pointed out that the material culture of Erlitou was extremely successful. It reached out to many other regions such as the middle Yangtze River, which means that the local people accepted some elements of the Erlitou culture. But it remains unclear whether it was ultimately due to the movement of objects, people or ideas. For instance, even the same object can be used and perceived in a completely different way in different contexts.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to say whether priests or other similar types of occupations existed in the period of Erlitou.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Almost certainly. From archaeological records, the social wealth that was required to support one ritual ceremony was clearly beyond what individuals could afford. It could be paid by big families or the central polity.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: This is a projection based on the Shang dynasty. The oracle bones reveal that the Shang kings were also the diviners (贞人) who were responsible for organising the divination and interpreting the results. Given the important role played by the ritual activities at Erlitou, it appears very likely that the head of the polity and the head of religion were the same figure (or the same group).

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Possible. See the notes above.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: It is very likely divination was supported by the polity.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: In fact, iconography is mainly preserved on the object, such as the abstract animal face like taotie on bronze or bone artefacts. The term taotie comes from much younger text written during the Eastern Zhou or the Han dynasty. It was the later scholars (e.g., Song dynasty) who chose this term to describe the main part of the decoration on the body as taotie.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Notes: It is virtually impossible to classify the nature of religion at Erlitou. Given the overall size of Erlitou, it was probably the largest one in the region of the Yi-Luo Rivers, which supported more than ten thousand people (the exact number varies significantly depending on different methods). Some top elite tombs show relatively similar burial practices (e.g., burial contents and tomb structure) so it might be possible that they follow the same religious belief. However, there is a lack of materials to argue that on the whole how many religious groups existed at Erlitou and what their relationship could be.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The ceremonial section is located on the central line of the whole site, which indicates its importance.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to know how many leaders were at Erlitou purely based on the burial materials without text. Some tombs show very exotic contents which were certainly not accessible by others, indicative of their very high social status. But it remains unclear in what social aspect, military, political or religious?

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Field doesn't know

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It might be yes. Albeit the lack of text, since Erlitou was primarily based on agricultural practice therefore local climate was essential to them. Their religion, if it involved supernatural power, was probably related to the climate or weather.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– Optional (rare)

Notes: Erlitou is often regarded as part of the origin of Chinese civilisation so some modern groups sometimes choose to organize ritual ceremonies here for worshipping ancestors or paying respect to the legends or ancient history.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The religion represented by Erlitou can be only understood through material remains and unfortunately, no written records have been discovered. There appears no doubt that Erlitou people were in frequent contact with other groups from different directions and many religion-related objects such as jade, bronze ritual vessels and dragon-shaped turquoise show a close connection with the late Neolithic people and other contemporary groups.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although no solid evidence can be provided, it appears that Erlitou normally invested a considerable amount of social wealth (animals, crops, or human sacrifices) in the ritual ceremonies, which were very likely related to certain type(s) of religion. This certainly required a system for collection and mobilization of these key resources. Therefore assigning religious affiliation could be envisaged.

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Notes: It is very likely divination was supported by the polity.

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– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: So far, it is still extremely difficult to provide an estimation of the overall population size at Erlitou, not to mention a specific type of people.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

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Notes: As noted in the previous question.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

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Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

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Notes: After decades of excavation, neither Erlitou nor Erligang (Zhengzhou) has yielded any sign of writing. It is either because these records were not easily preserved in deposition (e.g., organic materials) or they never existed.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Only some house foundations (rammed-earth) and associated ceremonial pits or burials have been discovered in the ritual and palatial section at Erlitou. The house foundations show in round or square, ranging from a few to circa one hundred square metres. In ceremonial pits or burials are often discovered elite objects such as jade, bronzes, lacquer, or turquoise.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 12.5

Notes: The ritual/ceremonial section in the north of Erlitou is often regarded as religious. Plus a few places in the palatial section which were also likely religious, the overall percentage could be around 10-15%

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 84

Notes: This is the largest house foundation which can be associated with ritual practice at Erlitou (84YLVIFI, north-south 12 meters and east-west 7 meters).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

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↳ Height of average monument, meters:

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– Percentage of area: 12.5

Notes: Erlitou was the largest settlement in this period.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Some tombs are very likely to be associated with religious activities, particularly those located in the ritual section of Erlitou. The elite tombs are also likely related to religion but difficult to tell precisely in which aspects.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Some house foundations are round, indicative of altars at Erlitou.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Many ceremonial pits are excavated with animal sacrifices and other material wealth (e.g., jade). For instance, some animal remains were carefully laid out, suggesting a deliberate decision.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some large houses around a few hundred square metres could be used for mass gathering point. But it is hard to tell whether it is specifically related to religion.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: In fact, iconography is mainly preserved on the object, such as the abstract animal face like taotie on bronze or bone artefacts. The term taotie comes from much younger text written during the Eastern Zhou or the Han dynasty. It was the later scholars (e.g., Song dynasty) who chose this term to describe the main part of the decoration on the body as taotie.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The ceremonial section is located on the central line of the whole site, which indicates its importance.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: Erlitou is often regarded as part of the origin of Chinese civilisation so some modern groups sometimes choose to organize ritual ceremonies here for worshipping ancestors or paying respect to the legends or ancient history.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2022 CE

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to discuss the distinction between spirit and body without detailed textual information.

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One can see a close connection between Erlitou and previous neolithic power based on the material records. It is likely that some previous human spirits were also passed down to Erlitou.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some abstract animal patterns were applied to important artifacts such as jade or bronze which were almost certainly used in a ritual ceremony. However, the difficulty lies in finding solid evidence to link these animal patterns to supernatural beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Again, no textual information is preserved to explore these issues at Eritou.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to specify who were the adherents of a certain type of religion at Eritou.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:
– Yes

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Include various species such as cattle, sheep/goat, pigs etc.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: It is very likely that the objects buried in the lower-elite or ordinary people's tombs were possessed by them during their lifetime. Those objects such as bronze ritual vessels were also likely used before entering into the deposition, although this is yet to be verified by scientific analysis in the future. Some bronze weapons and tools, in accordance with their alloying composition, were not made for practical use. They might have been made for just display or burial purposes.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: A number of tombs are excavated with jades, bronzes, lacquer, turquoises, or high-quality ceramics/bone artifacts.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Ordinary people were often buried with a few pieces of ceramics.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Ivory, proto-porcelain or white pottery (made with relatively higher temperature and clay with better quality, likely originated to south China).

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Pottery is the most prevailing type of grave goods at Erlitou. Except for the types of objects mentioned above, in a few cases were also discovered wooden objects.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ancient DNA analysis may reveal this in the future.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Tombs are often found around the palatial section of Erlitou.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Multiple individuals buried in the same tomb/pit, indicative of captives or human sacrifices.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to discuss the distinction between spirit and body without detailed textual information.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Again, no textual information is preserved to explore these issues at Erlitou.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to specify who were the adherents of a certain type of religion at Erlitou.

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↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Include various species such as cattle, sheep/goat, pigs etc.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

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Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One can see a close connection between Eritou and previous neolithic power based on the material records. It is likely that some previous human spirits were also passed down to Eritou.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some abstract animal patterns were applied to important artifacts such as jade or bronze which were almost certainly used in a ritual ceremony. However, the difficulty lies in finding solid evidence to link these animal patterns to supernatural beings.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

- Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- No

Is an eschatology present:

- No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

- Field doesn't know

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many human sacrifices at Eritou could be groups of people outside Eritou. Without further scientific analysis, it remains difficult to comment on their origin or identity.

↳ Commoners:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Elites:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:
– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A number of infant jar burials were discovered at Erlitou. This was more widely distributed in the preceding period of the late Neolithic Longshan culture. Difficult to say whether it was related to religion at Erlitou or other factors.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:
– Field doesn't know

↳ To out-groups:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Destroyed:
– Yes

Notes: Destroyed burial contents were more popular in the late Neolithic and became increasingly rare in the early Shang period. At Erlitou, cases of deliberately destroyed artefacts before or during the burial process can be found with jade, pottery and bronzes.

↳ Other:
– Yes [specify]: All major groups of artefacts have been mentioned in the answers above. It should be noted that some organic materials which did not survive in deposition could also have been buried or destroyed.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

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– Field doesn't know

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"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

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Elites:

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– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Erlitou has long been regarded as the beginning of a state-level society in Chinese prehistory, primarily due to its large-scale settlement and production, technological advance and long-distance communication. Recently, with new discoveries being made in late Neolithic sites, it has been increasingly recognized that the Longshan culture had already entered into the state level since many of the megacentres in Longshan appear significantly larger than Erlitou

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The system of bureaucracy at Erlitou was very likely combined with its religion. In other words, people like the top-elites may have performed their social roles in both the bureaucracy and religion.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: There is virtually no written language of any kind at Erlitou.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No written records prove its existence but it is possible. Given the importance of agriculture at Erlitou, there must have been a sort of calendar to guide agricultural practice in different seasons.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because the state military power/bureaucracy and religion at Erlitou were likely combined with one another, it appears very difficult to distinguish whether the adherents participated in the military of the religion or the state.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: See answer above

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Examples are human sacrifices who were tortured or beheaded.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Erlitou has long been regarded as the beginning of a state-level society in Chinese prehistory, primarily due to its large-scale settlement and production, technological advance and long-distance communication. Recently, with new discoveries being made in late Neolithic sites, it has been increasingly recognized that the Longshan culture had already entered into the state level since many of the megacentres in Longshan appear significantly larger than Erlitou

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The system of bureaucracy at Eritou was very likely combined with its religion. In other words, people like the top-elites may have performed their social roles in both the bureaucracy and religion.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: See answer above

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Examples are human sacrifices who were tortured or beheaded.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Because the state military power/bureaucracy and religion at Erlitou were likely combined with one another, it appears very difficult to distinguish whether the adherents participated in the military of the religion or the state.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: There is virtually no written language of any kind at Erlitou.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No written records prove its existence but it is possible. Given the importance of agriculture at Erlitou, there must have been a sort of calendar to guide agricultural practice in different seasons.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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